

OCEAN:ICE News – July 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to July's OCEAN:ICE News! We're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE.

Read on to meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on the latest OCEAN:ICE activities, including the Digital Ocean Forum 2024, the OCEAN:ICE Work Package 3 Webinar, and our recently submitted deliverables. Additionally, mark your calendars for the upcoming IGS Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models 2024 and our exciting Climate Coffees. Discover where you can find OCEAN:ICE in action at various events.

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more news in August!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Jing Jin

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on Jing Jin, a polar oceanographer and climate modeller, at [University of Liverpool](#).

Read the feature on Jing [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

Digital Ocean Forum 2024

On the 13th of June there was a 'Digital Ocean Forum' meeting for the EU Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) held at the grand Palais des Académies in Brussels. The DTO is now two years into an ambitious programme to provide a platform to deliver a multi-dimensional view of the ocean to end users, including scientists, citizens, industry, and policymakers. Whilst still a work in progress the DTO takes the two largest ocean data services, Copernicus Marine Services and EMODnet, and integrates them together into a core infrastructure and interface: EDITO-Infra.

OCEAN:ICE attended this event, which consisted of a number of technical demonstrations, end user discussions and future roadmaps. It also attended and contributed to the 'Technical and Scientific workshop' event on the 12th of June, where the nuts and bolts of the EDITO-Infra interface were explored, alongside discussion groups about future direction and opportunities. In its present form EDITO-Infra provides a cloud-based interface with the 'data lake' of the above datacentres products, on which users are able to build models of various complexity, using the dedicated cloud compute facilities of the DTO. These models, once properly validated, may be made available to end users.

Read more highlights from the Digital Ocean Forum 2024 on our [website](#).

OCEAN:ICE Work Package 3 Webinar

The second OCEAN:ICE Webinar introducing the Work Package 3, *Antarctica: Ice Sheet Mass Balance, Forcing and Dynamics*, took place on the 27th of June 2024. WP3 focuses on providing updated values and uncertainties for freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet to the ocean over the satellite observational period to the present day, including surface melt and runoff, ice flow, basal melt and calving.

This webinar featured talks by Work Package 3 Lead Dr. Ruth Mottram and senior scientists, Elizabeth Case, Gaël Durand, Keith Nicholls and Anastasiia Chyhareva, that were followed by a public Q&A session. The webinar was conducted as a part of the webinar series facilitated by the European Polar board (EPB), moderated by the EPB Policy Officer, Griffith Couser.

We thank all the speakers, and we are looking forward to the next webinar.

Catch our latest webinar and stay tuned for upcoming ones on our [website](#).

OCEAN:ICE Deliverables Submitted

The OCEAN:ICE community has been busy recently submitting several deliverables:

- D1.12 '[Record of Water Mass Age and Meltwater Fractions, Weddell Sea](#)'
- D1.4 '[Gridded European Circumpolar Sea Ice Production Fluxes](#)'

The progress and results of OCEAN:ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN:ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE at IGS Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models 2024

The OCEAN:ICE project will be strongly represented at the [IGS Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models](#), which is due to take place at Northumbria University in UK from 4 to 9 August 2024. The symposium is organised by the OCEAN:ICE work package 4 PI Jan De Rydt, and various members from WP3 (Ruth Mottram, Hilmar Gudmundsson) and WP4 (Frank Pattyn) are members of the science steering committee.

The symposium will share contributions by the international research community on a wide range of topics in the field of cryospheric model verification and validation, covering a range of different length and timescales. Contributions primarily focus on numerical model developments, process-based studies, and novel observational products, with the aim to improve numerical models of the cryosphere, and their interactions with the climate system.

The deadline for [registration](#) is 19 July 2024.

The banner features a background of a blue, textured ice surface. In the top left corner is the OCEAN:ICE logo, which includes a globe icon and the text 'OCEAN:ICE'. In the top right corner is the IGS 2024 logo, featuring a stylized mountain range and the text 'IGS 2024', 'Bringing Data and Models Together', and 'Northumbria University'. The main text in the center reads 'OCEAN:ICE at IGS' in large white letters, followed by '4-9 August 2024 | Newcastle' in smaller white letters. In the bottom left corner is the European Union flag. In the bottom right corner, there is a text block stating: 'OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation'.

Climate Coffee

[Oliver Huhn](#) on [Record of Water Mass Age and Meltwater Fractions, Weddell Sea](#)
1 August 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Oliver Huhn

Record of water mass age and meltwater fractions, Weddell Sea

1 August 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Mathilde Helbert on [Temporal and spatial length scales in \$\delta^{18}O\$ observations](#)

5 September 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Mathilde Helbert

Temporal and spatial length scales in $\delta^{18}O$ observations

5 September 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Hjalte Jomo Danielsen Sørup on User Engagement in developing high-resolution Urban Heat Island models: CLIM4cities project
12 September 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).
Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Hjalte Jomo Danielsen Sørup

User Engagement in developing high-resolution Urban Heat Island models: CLIM4cities project

12 September 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

CLIM4 CITIES

CLIMCoffee is under a programme of, and funded by, the European Space Agency. Views expressed do not reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

[Xabier Davila](#) on Tracing Freshwater Sources - Estimates from Salinity and Seawater Isotope Relationships
3 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).
Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Xabier Davila

Tracing Freshwater Sources - Estimates from Salinity and Seawater Isotope Relationships

3 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Ana Oliveira on CLIM4cities ML and AI Modelling
17 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).
Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Ana Oliveira

**AI for Urban Climate: An EO-Based
Approach for Heatwaves Exposure and
Adaptation – CLIM4cities project**

17 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

CLIM4
CITIES

CLIM4cities is under a programme of, and funded by, the European Space Agency. Views expressed do not reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 4-9 August 2024, [International Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models](#), Newcastle
- 19-23 August 2024, [11th SCAR Open Science Conference](#), Pucón & online
- 21-23 August 2024, [Nordic Meteorologist Meeting](#), Copenhagen
- 2-6 September 2024, [Challenger Society Conference](#), Oban
- 3-6 September 2024, [European Polar Science Week](#), Copenhagen

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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